
Harmonisation of access quality management and monitoring procedures for multi-RI TNA

General information

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Table of contents

Executive Summary	5
Glossary	5
1 Introduction	6
2 Method	6
3 Guidelines and monitoring procedures for quality management of TNA and VA projects...	7
4 References	9
5 Annexes	9

Executive Summary

The present deliverable D4.1 Harmonisation of access quality management and monitoring procedures for multi-RI TNA – establishes the framework under which Agro-Serv consortium will ensure a high-quality management and monitoring of TNA projects. To ensure that the quality management of access to each RI and that the monitoring of TNA-VA projects is achieved following harmonized procedures and to develop good practices, two documents were developed and are provided to access managers and users:

- i) A TNA - VA Term sheet that gathers all general principles about implementing a TNA or a VA project and clarifying in a flexible document both the host installations and the user(s)' rights and obligations.
- ii) A template for reports from user's and access managers in order to monitor the TNA-VA projects and obtain detailed information about the progress of the TNA-VA projects and improve the commissioning process and operation of TNA-VA projects

Glossary

Term	Description
Access Manager	Manager of access and service provision in a Research Infrastructure
Access provider	Manage of a specific installation or service within an organisation that is a member of a Research infrastructure
Agro-Serv	The present project
DMP	Data Management Plan : guidelines for management of data within AgroServ
Installation	Facility or service for the implementation of a specific service, a synonym a facility specifically with respect to access to experimental services
Review Panel	Panel of independent experts that will assess the Transnational Access applications
RI	Research Infrastructure
TNA	Trans-National Access. Allowing third party researchers from a foreign institution to access an organisation's research facilities and services.
VA	Virtual Access. Allowing third-party researchers to access an organisation's cloud, data centre, and/or its other IT facilities and services.
WP	Work Package. A set of related activities within a project.

1 Introduction

In the AgroServ project one of the key instruments is the provision of transnational physical access (TNA), remote and virtual access (VA) to research services that will enable cross disciplinary research needed for agroecological transition. The research in this area is by nature cross-disciplinary, and AgroServ TNA has to enable interaction of communities of researchers in widely separated areas. Thus, AgroServ integrates diverse scientific expertise from 11 ESFRI RIs (both projects and landmarks) contributing to different aspects of agroecology. AgroServ will allow users access to scientific data, highly specialized expertise, experimental sites, technology and laboratories integrating competences from chemists, biologists, plant and animal scientists, ecologists, bioengineers, analysts, sociologists, economists etc. A specific objective of AgroServ project is to provide multi-RIs services to ensure the cross-disciplinary needed for studies on Agroecology transition. The present document summarizes the guidelines to harmonize the access quality management and the monitoring procedures for multi-RI TNA and VA.

1.1 Objective and scope

The objective is to ensure that the quality management of access to each RI and that the monitoring of TNA-VA projects is achieved following harmonized procedures and to develop good practices. A specific objective is to identify and address access quality management issues for multi-RI accesses to customized services, in the context of sustainable and resilient agriculture and agro-ecological transitions.

2 Method

A quality management discussion group and an Ethical TNA committee composed of representatives of each RI were set up at the beginning of the project.

Name of RI	Quality management Discussion group		Ethical TNA committee	
	Name	E-mail	Name	E-mail
EU-Openscreen	Robert Harmel	robert.harmel@eu-openscreen.eu	Robert Harmel	robert.harmel@eu-openscreen.eu
MIRRI	Emmanuelle Helloin	Emmanuelle.helloin@inrae.fr	Sylvie Cranenbrouck	sylvie.cranenbrouck@uclouvain.be
Elixir	Cyril Pommier	cyril.pommier@inrae.fr	Cyril Pommier	cyril.pommier@inrae.fr
Euro-Biolmaging	Camilo Guzman	camilo.guzman@eurobioimaging.eu	Ilari Pulli	ilari.pulli@eurobioimaging.eu
EMPHASIS	Roland Pieruschka	r.pieruschka@fz-juelich.de	Sven Fahrner	s.fahrner@fz-juelich.de
EMBRC	Gemma Giménez Papiol	gemma.gimenez_papiol@sorbonne-universite.fr	Maria Huete	maria.huete@uvigo.es
AnaEE	Lavanya Premvardhan	lavanya.premvardhan@anaee.eu	Lavanya Premvardhan	lavanya.premvardhan@anaee.eu
SmartCow	Marta Terre (IRTA)	marta.terre@irta.cat	Emer Kennedy (Teagasc)	Emer.Kennedy@teagasc.ie
MetroFood	Chiara Nobili	chiara.nobili@enea.it		
IBISBA	Diana Garcia-Bernet	diana.garcia-bernet@inrae.fr	Diana Garcia-Bernet	diana.garcia-bernet@inrae.fr
LifeWatch	Iria SOTO	iria.soto@lifewatch.eu	Iria SOTO	iria.soto@lifewatch.eu

Documents used by each individual RI to evaluate the quality of access and to monitor the TNA projects were collected and shared on the cloud space of the AgroServ project. These documents were analyzed in common by the discussion group in order to harmonize the procedures and promote good practices in close coordination with WP1 and WP2.

3 Guidelines and monitoring procedures for quality management of TNA and VA projects

The proposed guidelines and monitoring procedures are in line with general user access guidelines for TNA defined by WP1 (D1.2) and AgroServ access policy (D.1.3). They refer also to the general ethical guidelines of the AgroServ project (D9.3). They are organized according the lifetime of a TNA project, by distinguishing three phases: During submission phase and before the start of the project, during service provision and after service provision (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Milestones in the TNA call and service provision.

The specific aspects of ethical assessments are the subject of D4.2.

3.1 During submission phase and before the start of the project

During the preparation of the submission and at the latest before the start of the project, it is highly recommended that the access managers of the RIs involved in the project and the applicants/users agree on the host installations and the user(s)' rights and obligations. Therefore, we provide a TNA – VA Term sheet as guidelines to check and discuss all necessary aspects.

This TNA - VA Term sheet (**see section 5, Annex 1**) gathers all general principles about implementing a TNA or a VA project and clarifying in a flexible document both the host installations and the user(s)' rights and obligations. This aims at ensuring that partners and users

work together in a transparent environment in terms of rules governing the TNA or VA and confidentiality.

We are including in this term sheet the rules governing the user(s)'s visit, use of material, data, obligation of reporting and dissemination, etc. In other words, the responsibility of each party.

We therefore envisaged this Term Sheet as a sort of check list (non-binding contract) broad enough to be adaptable to each partner organization with the intention:

- NOT to make a contract or force partners to use the document
- to propose guidelines to help RI access managers: several blocks of 'rules' that they could use to draft their own contract
- to anticipate how to solve problems if an issue arises / show that we have thought about it upstream.
- In case both parties agree, that some points may be fixed from the beginning (ex: cosigning a publication)
- to provide a sort of check list clearly mentioning the intentions of each party

3.2 During and after service provision

To harmonize and ensure a smooth and efficient monitoring of TNA-VA project a template for reports from user's and access managers is provided (**see section 5 – Annex 2**). Users and access managers shall fill in the templates in order to monitor the TNA-VA projects to obtain detailed information about the progress of the TNA-VA projects and improve the commissioning process and operation of TNA-VA projects. The templates shall be filled before the start of the project (report 1), at mid-point (report 2) only if the project is lasting more than 6 months and within 1 month after the end of the service provision (report 3). **There is a template for each report that can be filled online on the ISIA platform.**

At the end of the project, it is requested that the plan of dissemination and publication of the results of the project is defined.

In the final report a specific attention will be paid to:

- Scientific acknowledgement and co-authorship between users and RIs
- Impact on society (depending on project)
- Open Access of the publications
- Access to data: dataset published: FAIR principles
- Ethics/Social responsibility: Gender distribution of users (and seniority);
- Energy footprint (travel; resources etc)
- Academic/Industry users (SMEs)

3.3 Specific issues for multi-RI TNA-VA service provision

As AgroServ will provide multi-RI TVA-VA services, it is necessary that for projects involving 3 or more RIs a main access manager is defined.

4 References

- D1.2. General user access guidelines for TNA and VA
- D1.3. AgroServ access policy.
- D4.2. Protocol for ethical assessment of the submitted TNA proposals.
- D9.1. Project Management Guidelines. Version 1.
- D9.3. General Ethical Guidelines. Version 1.

5 Annexes

Annex 1: AgroServ TNA – VA Term Sheet

AgroServ TNA - VA AGREEMENT

Once signed, a scan of this Term Sheet should be sent to the AgroServ management team

TNA /VA Leader Name: _____

TNA Project short title (30 characters) from the application form:

Project Code and Acronym: _____

Installation #1 Name: _____ Country code: _____

Other Installations involved (please duplicate the line)

Number of physical visits: __

Visitor name	Arrival date <i>dd/mm/yyyy</i>	Departure date <i>dd/mm/yyyy</i>	No. of days considered for reimbursement ¹

Number of units of access agreed to be used in this project: _____

Maximum travel costs to be reimbursed for this project: _____ (€)

Deadline for implementing the project: _____

Deadline for sending the report to the RIs access managers: _____ *(date of end of experiment + 30 days)*

Deadline for providing the related Ethics documents to the TNA manager: _____

The applicant and access manager of the infrastructure have discussed the planned project and have agreed on: ***(please tick the appropriate boxes)***

- working regulations at the site, including insurance for the people involved
- technical access to be provided (equipment, consumables)
- technician support to be provided
- measurement/analyses services to be provided
- conditions of access to data and background knowledge of the host
- conditions for reimbursement by host organization have been explained to the user (forms, condition of reporting etc.)

¹ This information is meant to help calculate the reimbursement costs to the users.

- use and insurance of instruments brought by the user during the project
- sharing, reporting and publishing of the data and research results
- the TNA/VA application has been evaluated and both the applicant seeking access and the host facilities have confirmed the project.
- the user and the host have agreed on the conditions of project authorization regarding ethics.
- the user(s) and the host have read and agreed on the conditions for TNA/VA specified at the end of this document
- In each dissemination activity, users have to acknowledge the EC funding/project for their access: *The project leading to these results has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101058020 (AgroServ). This output reflects only the author's view and the European Union cannot be held responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.*

Upon signing the agreement, the applicant commits to report the results of the project to the AgroServ TNA access manager as soon as the TNA has come to an end, with a deadline of latest 30 days after the end of the experiment.

Participant #1:	Full Name (TNA/VA User): _____
Date, Location:	Signature:
Participant #2:	Full Name (TNA/VA User): _____
Date, Location:	Signature:
Installation #1	Full Name (TNA/VA Pilot Installation manager):
Date, Location:	_____
	Signature:
Installation #2	Full Name (TNA/VA Pilot Installation manager):
Date, Location:	_____
	Signature:

A separate specific agreement, whose nature will depend on the type of collaboration, may be signed between the hosts and the external users: it may either be a Research (partnership) agreement or a hosting or service provision agreement depending on the level of autonomy of the user, the type of support provided by the RI and if it is a joint RI/user research activity. This specific agreement will define the access rules to the RIs, in particular, to the Parties' laboratories, biological materials, equipment or to any other necessary resources. This agreement will have to include the elements listed in the different sections below.

The Parties (i.e. the host and the external user(s)) agree upon the following general principles:

1. General Principles for providing trans-national access to research infrastructure or virtual access²

Research Infrastructures should have an access policy defining how they **regulate, grant and support** Access to Users” (...)

- This installation has one: _____
(title/reference number of the document and where to find it)
- This installation doesn't have one

Research Infrastructures should have a **research data management policy**. Research Infrastructures and Users should have an **agreement on how to use the data**

- This installation has one: _____ (title/reference number of the document and where to find it)
- This installation doesn't have one

The Access providers must request written approval from the European Commission for the selection of user groups requiring visits to the installation(s) exceeding three months, unless otherwise specified in the description of the action.

In addition, the Access providers shall:

- advertise widely, including on a dedicated website, the access offered under this Grant Agreement;
- promote equal opportunities in advertising the access and take into account the gender dimension when defining the support provided to users;
- ensure that users comply with the terms and conditions of AgroServ Grant Agreement;
- ensure that its obligations under Articles 12 (conflict of interest), 13 (confidentiality), 17 (visibility of EU funding) and 33 (liability for damages) of the Grant Agreement also apply to the users.

2. Transnational access and virtual access agreements³

The agreement to be signed between the host organization and the user shall foresee the following elements:

- i) **The hosting of External Users' staff in the premises of the Parties** shall be subject to a hosting agreement. This agreement shall define, amongst other elements, the purpose of the hosting and relevant intellectual property rules;
- ii) **All access rights to the Background and to Results of the Parties** shall be subject to prior approval of the owning Party/ies, via a license agreement. The access rights shall be granted on a non-exclusive and non-transferable basis;

Before the implementation of the TNA project (during the application), the parties (users and RI managers) should determine the background of the host to which they are ready to grant access rights. Conversely, both parties should agree that all background not listed in this notice shall be explicitly excluded from access right.

² Grant Agreement Article 16

³ Grant Agreement Article 16

- iii) **Access and exchange of biological material and software belonging to the Parties** to External Users shall be subject to the signature of a material transfer agreement (MTA⁴);
- iv) **Access to the AgroServ RIs by the External Users** will be subject to the signature of a specific agreement which shall, in particular, define the conditions of use of the RIs, the financial terms and the rules of intellectual property which will apply in the frame of this access. In particular, if the staff employed by the involved RIs effectively works and cooperates with the External User, a partnership agreement shall be signed in the conditions defined at v) hereinafter;
- v) **When within the frame of a research programme set on a common initiative**, the Parties and the External Users shall sign a partnership agreement. The Parties and the External Users shall agree to share the intellectual property of all the Results developed during this programme;
- vi) **The Parties shall ensure that External Users have signed all necessary insurance policies** to insure their activity against all risks and liabilities lying upon them;
- vii) **The conditions of confidentiality, publication and communication** shall be expressly mentioned in any of the above mentioned specific agreements signed between the External Users and the concerned Parties.

3. Reporting and Dissemination

- As a condition for funding, each TNA user/user group which has been granted access to AgroServ infrastructure is committed to provide a report⁵ to the AgroServ TNA/VA management team on the experiment carried out, and the results. This will be communicated to the EU⁶ and will allow the users to benefit from AgroServ advertisement through the project's communication tools (newsletter, website...).
- **Dissemination** of TNA project's results is mandatory for TNA and VA users, unless they are working for SMEs⁷. It can be delayed until IP has been investigated. Dissemination can be done either by depositing the data in the project database or as a scientific publication. We encourage you to do both or any other ways that are allowing a dissemination of the results.
- In each dissemination activity, users should acknowledge the EC funding/project for their access: *The project leading to these results has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101058020 (AgroServ). This output reflects only the author's view and the European Union cannot be held responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.*
- In case of scientific publication, we encourage the user/user group to publish in **open access**, either gold (paid for) or green (author version in a public repository).

⁴ Material/Data transfer agreement template or any agreement used in your institution that respect AgroServ Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement

⁵ The AgroServ team is providing a report template for TNA and VA monitoring (see « Templates for reports from user and facility managers »)

⁶ It will not be published or put in open access without the user's consent.

⁷ Grant Agreement Article 16

4. Costs for TNA (visits and experiments) and deviations

Conditions for reimbursement shall be compliant with the internal rules of the host institutions. The maximum rates of reimbursement of travel and subsistence costs have been set by the individual **research infrastructures as described (Where is it described ?)**

In case the TNA experiment implies that the users' visit is longer than 7 consecutive days, weekends shall be taken into account for the reimbursement of the user (daily allowance). The same happens in case there is a national holiday during the stay.

The time required for local staff support should be estimated before the start of the TNA project's implementation and be mentioned in the contract.

Deviations

- Any change, in the limit of 25% of the total number of units of access initially validated by the Selection Panel, for the same TNA project requires an agreement between the User and the Host. If the difference of number of units of access exceeds 25% or leads to a new project, it will have to go through a reviewing process again (SmartCow Selection Panel).
- Any change in personnel on the project requires authorization by the Host and Selection Panel. A CV of the substitute person must be sent to the AgroServ TNA management team.
- Any change in the travel dates and number of days initially agreed for the stay of the user shall be first validated with the host. The host may refuse to reimburse these costs if it was not informed and did not agree before the change occurred.
- Unpredictable problems and Force Majeure: on the host side, some deviations may occur out of its control: impossibility to perform the experiments because of weather conditions or for technical or biological reasons (e.g. animal death or illness, broken apparatus, instrumentation damage, illness, flight cancellation). In this case, AgroServ will not cover the need for extra-budget, if any, but an agreement will have to be sought between the host and the user to postpone the experiment and/or the visit in order to complete the TNA project.
- Unforeseen costs: any need to use facilities or supplies that were not previously anticipated by the host and the users (analyses, chemicals, shipping to/from the Infrastructure etc.) may lead to additional costs for the users unless the host accepts to cover them. The level of reliance of the user on the local RI staff should be anticipated by the host and the user through telephone/video conference or any other relevant means as early as possible and before the visit/the beginning of the experiment.
- In case of use of hazardous products and/or biohazards conditions, of specific health and safety conditions in the host facilities or in case of need for field collection of resources (permits), specific clauses will be added in the agreement.

Annex 2: AgroServ Template for report from TNA and VA projects

(The templates shall be filled online on the ISIA platform)

Project Title	
User Name and email	
User affiliation	
Access managers/providers	

Date of delivery report	Experiment	Report planned	Actual
Report 1 – start ⁸			
Report 2 – mid-point			
Report 3 - end⁹			

Authors (Users and access providers)				
Responsible Author (User)	Name		Email	
Responsible Author (access manager)	Name		Email	

⁸ The start is equal to the date where the operations are starting

⁹ + 30 days after the end of the project

Report 1 – Due date: start of the project

Users please answer:

1. Are there any information missing in the call text at the webpage?

2. How did you contact the access providers before submitting the preproposal?

By email:	By skype/phone:	Both email and meeting:
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3. How did you contact the access providers before submitting the proposal?

By email:	By skype/phone:	Both email and meeting:
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4. Was it clear how to fill in the submission forms?

Yes:	No:	What is missing:
------	-----	------------------

5. How did you organize the preparation of the project with the installations?

6. Have you provided a detailed protocol of the experiment?

Yes:	No:
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7. Do you have a written contract /agreement besides the experimental protocol?

Yes:	No:
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8. What is the planned start date, mid-point and end data?

Start:	Mid-point:	End date:
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9. Have you agreed on dates for visits to the facility?

Visit planned from date:	to date:
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10. Did you get help with any ethical approval of the project?

Yes:	No:
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11. Have you provided the user with guidelines or written information about Standard Operating Procedures (SOP) at your installation? (**access manager please answer the following questions**)

Yes:	No:	Why not?
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12. Do you have suggestions for good practice on how to present the installations and terms to prospective users

13. Have you a written agreement on which data, when and how the data should be delivered? **(Both users and access managers please answer)**

Yes:	No:	What is your expectations?
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14. Are there any extra cost for the facility related to the project not covered by AgroServ?

No:	Yes:	Do you have a written agreement on that? Yes:	No:
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15. Describe how and how often the user will get feedback from the facility.

User:
Access manager:

Report 2 – Due date: mid-point of the project if its duration is longer than 6 months

Users and access managers please both answer

1. Is the project delayed?

Access Manager Yes: No: Explain why:
Add new end data here:
User: Any comments:

2. Are there any deviations from the initial plan?

Access manager: No: Yes: Explain what, why and consequences:
User: Any comments:

3. How often have you been in contact?

Once a week: Once a month: Other interval:
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4. What was the character of the contact?

Email: Phone/skype meeting: With minutes written yes: No:
Visit of the ongoing experiment by the user:

5. Please suggest a good practice for communication between user and access manager

User:
Access manager:

6. Any other comments at the mid-point of the experiment

User:
Access manager:

Report 3 – Due date: End of the project + 30 days

Users and facility manager please answer:

1. Was the project delayed between the mid-point and end?

Access Manager Yes:	No:	Explain why:
User: Any comments:		

2. Were there any deviation from the plan from mid-point until the end

Access manager: No:	Yes: Explain what, why and consequences:
User: Any comments:	

3. Are all data handed out to the user?

Access manager: Yes:	No: Explain why and when this will happen
User: Any comments:	

4. How often have you been in contact?

Once a week:	Once a month:	Another interval:
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5. What was the character of the contact?

Email:	Phone/skype meeting:	With minutes written yes:	No:
Visit of the experiment by the users:			

6. Any suggestions for good practice on communications between user and access manager

User:
Access manager:

7. From start to end – what was the three most difficult issues to deal with?

User:
Access manager:

8. Any other suggestions for improvement

User:
Access Manager:

9. Did you have a meeting at the end of the project for evaluation?

Yes: No:
If yes please give the main points:

10. Do you expect to follow the plan for publication as in the proposal?

Yes: Add the time schedule.
No: Please explain why and add the new plan
Please remember the user are obligated to publish results from the TNA-VA projects

11. The main scientific outcome of the projects

<i>Please include a 2-3 pages report including:</i>

- The main objective of the project
- The hypothesis that are tested
- The main scientific outcome, innovation/impact of the results
- Any other achievements of the visit
- How do you expect to disseminate the results
- Any suggestions to improve the TNA procedure

Please take care of following issues in the final report;

- Scientific acknowledgement and co-authorship between users and RIs
- Impact on society (depending on project)
- Open Access of the publications
- Access to data: dataset published: FAIR principles
- Ethics/Social responsibility: Gender distribution of users (and seniority);
- Energy footprint (travel; resources etc)
- Academic/Industry users (SMEs)

